

Dual Unified Power Quality Conditioner with Proportional-Resonant Controller

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Abstract: The Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC) is an equipment that simultaneously mitigates voltage and current disturbances. It is formed by two active filters in a back-to-back configuration with a series connection to the grid by one of the converters, and the other is shunt-connected. Many researchers explore its control system using different strategies based on different theories. This paper presents the dual approach of the UPQC with proportional-resonant (PR) controllers substituting proportional-integral (PI) controllers. The use of this type of controller does not require mathematical tools to make the signal constant, such as the Park transformation, to make the tracking error zero in a steady state, which reduces the computational effort in real-time processing. Software simulations are done to validate the performance of the Dual UPQC with PR controllers. Comparisons with the PI strategy are presented as well.

Keywords: Dual UPQC, Proportional-Resonant Controller, Typhoon HIL, PI Controller, Power Quality, Power Electronics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of power electronics devices has been increasing fast in the last decades, mainly because of the growing penetration of distributed generation (DG). Despite many advantages of DG as a decarbonization contribution, power quality (PQ) issues tend to occur. Some kinds of solutions are applied in power systems, such as passive and active power filters, dynamic voltage restorer (DVR), and static synchronous compensator (STATCOM). An interesting custom power device presented in literature is the Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC), which is capable of mitigating voltage and current disturbances simultaneously Gade et al. (2021).

The UPQC is an equipment consisting of two active filters (AF) connected in a back-to-back configuration. One filter is connected to the grid through injection transformers on the source side of the Point of Common Coupling (PCC), while the other filter is connected in a shunt configuration on the load side, although it is not necessarily equipped with shunt transformers. There are some types of topology for the UPQC, each one with its different characteristics Singh et al. (1999); Gade et al. (2021). This paper is based on the dual topology of this device Aredes and

Fernandes (2009), which presents a simplification in the control system when compared to the classical approach of UPQC Fujita and Akagi (1998) as shown in Franca et al. (2011).

In this paper, the topology used is presented in Figure 1 through a single phase diagram representation, where V_s , V_{par} , V_{dc} , I_{ser} and I_L are important measured variables for the controller of this device.

Figure 1. Dual UPQC topology and its connection to the grid

A simplified diagram of the device is presented in Figure 2. In this configuration, the series AF functions as a current source, imposing an ideal fundamental current, i_{series} , which equals the compensated source current, i_{source} , thereby compensating for the distorted load current, i_{load} ,

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by directing it through the shunt converter node. Meanwhile, the shunt AF operates as a voltage source, imposing an ideal fundamental voltage, v_{shunt} , at the PCC and ensuring that the distorted voltage, v_{series} , remains confined to the injection transformers of the series converter, effectively compensating the load voltage, v_{load} .

Over the years, the equipment has been studied, and improvements have been proposed. One of the research topics is its control system. In Kesler and Ozdemir (2011), the synchronous reference frame is used as a control strategy. In Khadkikar and Chandra (2008), the voltage compensation is done through the power angle control. The first presented UPQC Fujita and Akagi (1998) has its control system based on the instantaneous power theory Akagi (2017). However, the conventional power theory can be applied, as shown in Monteiro et al. (2003).

Figure 2. Simplified Operation of Dual Unified Power Quality Conditioner

In UPQC control systems, the Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is widely used to generate reference signals for the PWM modulator, which controls converter switching [1]. However, transforming the $\alpha\beta$ reference into a dq reference frame to eliminate steady-state error introduces computational complexity. This paper proposes replacing PI controllers with Proportional-Resonant (PR) controllers tuned to the fundamental frequency, reducing the need for trigonometric calculations. The performance of the controller is analyzed through simulations using Typhoon HIL software.

After this brief introduction, this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 shows the control system of the equipment, divided between reference signals calculation and modulation signals generation. After that, the PR controller theory is presented in Section 3. In Section 4, the paper proposal is described; Results are shown and discussed in Section 5. Then, Section 6 presents the conclusions and next steps of this work.

2. CONTROL SYSTEM OF THE DUAL UPQC

The dual approach of UPQC imposes fundamental voltage on the load bus and fundamental current on the source bus. In this way, the mitigation of voltage and current disturbances occurs indirectly. According to Kirchhoff's laws, if the grid voltage has disturbances and the shunt

converter imposes a voltage signal at the fundamental frequency on the load bus, the disturbances on the source side remain at the series converter terminals. Likewise, if the loads have current disturbances and the series converter imposes a current with a sinusoidal waveform at the fundamental frequency, the disturbances go to the shunt converter.

2.1 Voltage and Current References

The main stage of the dual UPQC control system, shown by Figure 3, was presented in Aredes and Fernandes (2009) and was improved in Franca et al. (2011). It is based on the p-q theory Akagi (2017) with $\alpha\beta$ -frame.

In the voltage control loop, which refers to the shunt converter, the measures of line-to-line source voltages, V_{s-ab} and V_{s-bc} , is transformed to Clarke's frame, followed by a synchronizing circuit composed of a q-PLL and a fundamental positive sequence detector Barbosa Rolim et al. (2006), that returns as output the grid fundamental frequency, ω_1 and phase, θ_1 , the ideal fundamental currents for the next step, i'_α and i'_β , and the fundamental positive sequence of source voltage in $\alpha\beta$ -frame, $v_{s+1-\alpha}$ and $v_{s+1-\beta}$. The Voltage Selector block is used then to generate the voltage references, $v_{ref-\alpha}$ and $v_{ref-\beta}$, based on the limitations of amplitude described in the Brazilian standard for electric power distribution procedures (ANEEL Normative Resolution No. 956/2021), ANEEL (2022).

The second component of the main controller is the series converter. The measured load currents, i_{L-a} and i_{L-b} , are transformed from the abc -frame to the $\alpha\beta$ -frame, and the average active power, \bar{p}_L , is calculated using the $v_{ref-\alpha}$ and $v_{ref-\beta}$ variables from the shunt control. By comparing the measured DC-link voltage, v_{dc} , with the desired DC-link voltage reference, a tracking error is generated, which serves as the input to a PI controller. This controller ensures that the DC-link voltage is maintained within the safe operational limits of the equipment. The output of the PI controller, representing the UPQC losses, \bar{p}_{loss} , is added to \bar{p}_L . The resulting active instantaneous power, \bar{p}_T , is then used to generate current reference signals by applying the p-q theory formulas once more. However, in this case, the output signals $v_{s+1-\alpha}$ and $v_{s+1-\beta}$ are used.

2.2 PWM References

The second part of the dual UPQC controller is the calculation of PWM references to both converters, also shown in Figure 3. Once PI controllers are used to reach zero error and the reference signals are sinusoidal, Park transformation is needed. In the same way, the signals of the AC voltage of the shunt converter and the AC current of the series converter are transformed to dq frame. Signals are compared, and the error goes to the PI controller. Output signals from PI are transformed back to $\alpha\beta$ frame and then to abc . Finally, the resulting signals are the modulation waves to be compared with a carrier signal. It can be noticed that in the control of the shunt converter there is a low-pass filter block and a positive feedback in order to increase the robustness, as explained in Franca et al. (2011).

Figure 3. Main control system of Dual UPQC

3. PROPORTIONAL-RESONANT CONTROLLER

PI controllers are widely used in power electronics control systems. However, the input signal must be constant to ensure a near-zero steady-state error, so the Park transformation is commonly used to rotate the reference of three-phase AC signals into the Direct-Quadrature-Zero ($DQ0$) reference frame.

An alternative to eliminate this need is the so-called resonant controller Blaabjerg (2018). There are some resonant controller topologies in the literature. This work uses the configuration presented in Teodorescu et al. (2006); Franca et al. (2022) with a proportional gain K_p added to its transfer function $R_h(s)$, presented in (1). The controller parameters to be configured for this type of controller are: the proportional gain K_p , the resonant gain K_h , which refers to the harmonic order h that the controller to be tuned; and the cutoff frequency ω_h . It is possible to see that this modeling is for only one harmonic order; therefore, for more harmonic orders, parallel connections of resonant controllers can be made where each harmonic control effort is added to the fundamental frequency control effort.

$$R_h(s) = K_p + K_h \cdot \frac{2\omega_h s}{s^2 + 2\omega_h s + (h\omega_1)^2} \quad (1)$$

4. METHODOLOGY

The dual UPQC was modeled in Typhoon HIL software, following the recommendations of Victor S. Monteiro et al. (2022). The three-phase diagram of the circuit used for the analysis is shown in Figure 4, with the main values. The system is similar to Victor S. Monteiro et al. (2022) and is composed of a non-linear load to generate distorted load currents, a linear two-phase load to generate load current unbalances and shunt resistors connected after the source to emulate a voltage sag on the load bus. The Dual UPQC must be able to compensate the source current and the load voltage at the PCC.

Figure 4. Case Study Modeled on Typhoon Hil

Typhoon HIL was chosen because this paper is part of a project dedicated to simulating the dual topology of a UPQC within a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) framework. The choice of Typhoon HIL is driven by its robust capabilities for real-time simulation and comprehensive HIL integration, which are essential for accurately modeling and analyzing the performance of the UPQC system in a controlled and realistic environment. This approach enables precise evaluation of system dynamics and control strategies before implementation in physical hardware.

The equipment with PI controllers was initially simulated as a comparative baseline. Although the steady-state and dynamic responses of the PI controllers were similar to those of the PR controllers, the key difference lies in the computational advantages of the PR controllers when both control systems are implemented. The PI controllers, which were replaced, are located in the reference section for the PWM modulation of the converters, as shown in Figure 5a. The modified control system incorporating PR controllers is illustrated in Figure 5b.

Figure 5. Comparison between PI (a) and Proportional-Resonant (b) Controllers.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figures 6a and 6b illustrate the disturbances in the source voltage and load current, respectively. The voltage sag, approximately 0.6 pu, caused by the shunt resistors on source bus is clearly observed, along with the highly distorted current caused by harmonics from the non-linear load and the imbalance introduced by the two-phase load.

The Figures 7a and 7b represent the compensations for the disturbances, with the load voltage being raised to approximately 1.0 pu due to the action of the shunt AF, Figure 7a, and the source current having its harmonics filtered and its phases balanced due to the action of the series AF of UPQC equipment in PCC, Figure 7b.

The THD of both the load voltage and source current was evaluated across three scenarios outlined in the base Case Study, as shown in Table 1. According to the PQ module specified in ANEEL (2022), the THD of the load voltage must be limited to 10.0 % of its fundamental component for systems with a nominal voltage below 2.3 kV. When the Dual UPQC with PR controllers is active, it successfully compensates the load voltage, maintaining it within

standard limits. To assess the capability of mitigating current distortion, a THD limit of 5.0 % of the fundamental was applied, as per IEEE (2022), for systems with nominal voltages between 127.0 V and 69.0 kV. However, in both PI and PR controller simulations, the current compensation results exceeded the standard limits. Addressing this issue has been incorporated into a project aimed at enhancing the prototyping method using Typhoon HIL software.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new strategy for the control system of a UPQC, in which the PI controllers traditionally used in PWM modulation are replaced by PR controllers. The simulations, conducted using Typhoon HIL for modeling and monitoring, provided conclusive evidence supporting the effectiveness of this type of controller within the equipment control system. These findings lay the foundation for future research and potential advancements in this field.

The proposal was validated through an analysis of simulation results, focusing on the THD of compensated voltage and current using PR controllers, and comparing them

(a) Distorted Source Voltage

(a) Compensated Source Voltage

(b) Distorted Load Current

(b) Compensated Load Current

Figure 6. Distorted signals

Figure 7. Compensated signals

Table 1. THD of both compensated Voltage and Current

Electrical Magnitude	Non-Linear Load Case		Non-Linear and Two-Phase Linear Case		Non-Linear, Two-Phase Linear Voltage Sag Case	
	Without UPQC	PR Controller	Without UPQC	PR Controller	Without UPQC	PR Controller
$V_{load-AB}$	10.83 %	8.01 %	10.60 %	7.91 %	1.93 %	7.12 %
$V_{load-BC}$	10.87 %	6.61 %	10.18 %	6.34 %	2.06 %	6.34 %
$V_{load-CA}$	10.84 %	6.59 %	10.46 %	6.66 %	2.26 %	6.07 %
$I_{source-A}$	21.09 %	6.29 %	13.49 %	5.37 %	16.40 %	4.62 %
$I_{source-B}$	21.11 %	6.52 %	19.80 %	4.38 %	23.46 %	4.86 %
$I_{source-C}$	21.12 %	6.26 %	10.49 %	4.91 %	13.62 %	4.65 %

against the limits set by national and international standards.

The main gain of the proposed change is that the control algorithm embedded in the equipment's microcontroller has a reduced computational load, since the PR does not require the mathematical operations of the Park transform to guarantee a steady-state error close to zero.

In future work, HIL functionality will be implemented using a microcontroller interfaced with Typhoon HIL hardware to simulate the power system in real-time. Additionally, a comparative analysis will be conducted to assess the computational burden of control systems employing Proportional-Resonant (PR) controllers versus other types of controllers. This analysis aims to evaluate the relative effectiveness of PR controllers in comparison to alternative strategies

It is important to add that this work makes a valuable contribution to UPQC research, since the proposed modification can improve the real-time processing performance of equipment control.

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REFERENCES

- Akagi, H. (2017). *Instantaneous power theory and applications to power conditioning*. IEEE Press series on power engineering. IEEE Press/Wiley, Hoboken, New Jersey, second edition edition. OCLC: ocn975024781.
- ANEEL (2022). Aneel normative resolution no. 956/2021. URL <https://www.gov.br/aneel/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudos/procedimentos-regulatorios/prodist>.
- Aredes, M. and Fernandes, R.M. (2009). A unified power quality conditioner with voltage SAG/SWELL compensation capability. In *2009 Brazilian Power Electronics Conference*, 218–224. IEEE, Bonito-Mato Grosso do Sul. doi:10.1109/COBEP.2009.5347700. URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5347700/>.
- Barbosa Rolim, L.G., Rodrigues Da Costa, D., and Aredes, M. (2006). Analysis and Software Implementation of

- a Robust Synchronizing PLL Circuit Based on the pq Theory. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 53(6), 1919–1926. doi:10.1109/TIE.2006.885483. URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/4016391/>.
- Blaabjerg, F. (ed.) (2018). *Control of power electronic converters and systems*. Academic Press, London. OCLC: ocn983340487.
- Franca, B.W., Da Silva, L.F., and Aredes, M. (2011). Comparison between alpha-beta and DQ-PI controller applied to IUPQC operation. In *XI Brazilian Power Electronics Conference*, 306–311. IEEE, Natal, Brazil. doi:10.1109/COBEP.2011.6085231. URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6085231/>.
- Franca, B.W., Aredes, M., Silva, L.F.D., Gontijo, G.F., Tricarico, T.C., and Posada, J. (2022). An Enhanced Shunt Active Filter Based on Synchronverter Concept. *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, 10(1), 494–505. doi:10.1109/JESTPE.2021.3103836. URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9509838/>.
- Fujita, H. and Akagi, H. (1998). The unified power quality conditioner: the integration of series- and shunt-active filters. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 13(2), 315–322. doi:10.1109/63.662847. URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/662847/>.
- Gade, S., Agrawal, R., and Munje, R. (2021). Recent trends in power quality improvement: Review of the unified power quality conditioner. *ECTI-EEC*, 19(3), 268–288.
- IEEE (2022). Ieee standard for harmonic control in electric power systems. *IEEE Std 519-2022 (Revision of IEEE Std 519-2014)*, 1–31. doi:10.1109/IEEESTD.2022.9848440.
- Kesler, M. and Ozdemir, E. (2011). Synchronous-reference-frame-based control method for upqc under unbalanced and distorted load conditions. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 58(9), 3967–3975. doi:10.1109/TIE.2010.2100330.
- Khadkikar, V. and Chandra, A. (2008). A new control philosophy for a unified power quality conditioner (upqc) to coordinate load-reactive power demand between shunt and series inverters. *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, 23(4), 2522–2534. doi:10.1109/TPWRD.2008.921146.
- Monteiro, L., Aredes, M., and Moor Neto, J. (2003). A control strategy for unified power quality conditioner. In *2003 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (Cat. No.03TH8692)*, volume 1, 391–396 vol. 1. doi:10.1109/ISIE.2003.1267280.

- Singh, B., Al-Haddad, K., and Chandra, A. (1999). A review of active filters for power quality improvement. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 46(5), 960–971. doi:10.1109/41.793345. URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/793345/>.
- Teodorescu, R., Blaabjerg, F., Liserre, M., and Loh, P. (2006). Proportional-resonant controllers and filters for grid-connected voltage-source converters. *IEE Proceedings - Electric Power Applications*, 153(5), 750. doi:10.1049/ip-epa:20060008. URL https://digital-library.theiet.org/content/journals/10.1049/ip-epa_20060008.
- Victor S. Monteiro, Mateus C. Costa, and Bruno W. França (2022). Simulação no software Typhoon HIL para equipamentos de eletrônica de potência compostos por múltiplos conversores. Online. doi: 10.20906/CBA2022/3744. URL https://sba.org.br/open_journal_systems/index.php/cba/article/view/3744.